

Complete flow characterization from snapshot PIV, fast probes and physics-informed neural networks

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) are function approximators that can incorporate physics laws during training. In recent years, PINNs have been shown to be capable of reconstructing fluid behavior using constraints based on the Navier–Stokes equations and field data. On the downside, the lack of time resolution in a wide range of experimental applications severely limits the applicability of PINNs. We propose a novel methodology based on feeding PINNs with time-resolved fields estimated from non-time-resolved field measurements (e.g. particle image velocimetry) and time-resolved pointprobe measurements (e.g. hot-wires). First, the dimensionality of the problem is reduced by using as a target the temporal modes from a truncated proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) of the velocity fields. Then, using a multilayer perceptron (MLP), a correspondence is established between probe data and the POD time coefficients of the velocity fields. The estimated fields are then fed to the PINN to enhance the data and increase precision. As a further benefit, additional derived quantities not available in the raw data, such as the pressure distribution, can be extracted if suitable boundary conditions are provided. We validate the method on synthetic test cases based on the direct numerical simulation of the wake of a fluidic pinball. Furthermore, we test the algorithm in an experimental case of the wake of a stalled wing. The results show that the PINN is able

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to reduce the error in the estimated fields, provided that the reference data obtained from the estimation with the MLP are sufficiently accurate.

1. Introduction

The use of machine-learning (ML) algorithms is experiencing a continuous expansion in an ever-growing amount of applications thanks to the increase of the computational capacity as well as the speed at which results can be obtained. Fluid mechanics has also benefited from the advances of ML in several fields, including modeling and control [1], as well as enhancement of experiments [2] and simulations [3]. ML has demonstrated being a powerful ally to recover, correct, regularize or enhance (among other capabilities) experimental data that otherwise would be corrupted or not accessible due to setup or hardware limitations. The recently-developed physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) [4,5] are an example of a function approximator based on a neural network architecture which is trained by directly enforcing physical constraints generically expressed in the form of ordinary or partial differential equations [6]. In their original implementation, PINNs were based on fully-connected layers which incorporate compliance with respect to governing laws as loss function and therefore are able to impose physics constraints while reconstructing field variables from incomplete or limited measurements or data. PINNs have already been used in a large variety of applications, such as heat transfer [7], cardiovascular flows [8], power systems [9], optics [10], and many more [11–16].

In the field of fluid mechanics, PINNs have been proven to provide promising results regarding fluid flow estimation [5] using scalar field data. Recently, PINNs have been used to obtain dense velocity fields from Lagrangian particle tracking measurements [17, 18]. However, data assimilation via PINNs requires adequate temporal resolution to accurately compute the time derivatives in the Navier–Stokes (NS) equations. This is often problematic to achieve due to hardware limitations, which in some cases may not even be overcome with expensive equipment. Consequently, the use of PINNs for non-time-resolved particle image velocimetry (PIV), often referred to as ‘snapshot PIV’, has been limited so far to the estimation of flow statistics based on Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations [19].

To overcome the lack of time resolution, several studies have aimed at predicting flow fields via multi-time delay linear estimators (and more recently nonlinear mapping based on neural networks) using pointprobes, for which time resolution is more accessible, in combination with snapshot PIV. While this approach comes at the expense of increased complexity of the setup, it has been demonstrated to be an interesting solution to obtain time-resolved flow field measurements. Estimators based on linear stochastic estimation (LSE) [20] and extended proper orthogonal decomposition (EPOD) [21] have been proven effective to obtain good estimations of the most energetic flow features. This approach has been leveraged in several applications, including jet flows [22], wall-mounted obstacles [23], wakes [24–26] and wall-bounded flows [27,28]. More recently, nonlinear estimators based on shallow neural networks [29], convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [30,31], generative adversarial networks (GANs) [32] and recurrent neural networks such as long short-term memory (LSTM) [33,34] have been proposed. While such methods have shown some success, especially in low-rank test cases, i.e. cases in which the flow information can be easily embedded in a handful of probes due to the dominance of certain flow features (such as shedding wakes), their accuracy has still margin of improvement in case of spectrally-richer flows.

In this work, we present a novel architecture consisting of PINNs as a regularizer for time-resolved flow fields estimated from fast pointprobes. This approach features several benefits. First, we enable the use of PINNs for non-time-resolved data by introducing time resolution through the combination of PIV with probes. Second, PINNs are expected to improve the accuracy of the reconstructed fields by imposing physical constraints. Third, with adequate boundary conditions, PINNs can augment the data by providing access to additional features, such as the pressure field.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the proposed algorithm and describes the used architecture. The validation on a synthetic test case based on the direct numerical simulation of a fluidic pinball is presented in Section 3. The proposed architecture is then tested on an experimental case, as illustrated in Section 4. Finally, the capabilities and limitations of the methods are discussed in the conclusions.

2. Methodology

2.1. Flow estimation architecture

A sketch of the new architecture proposed in this article is presented in Fig. 1. The first step is the construction of a latent space for the velocity fields to ease the mapping of the probes. This principle is normally leveraged in EPOD-based estimation. Its rationale is that, most often, turbulent flows evolve on low-dimensional attractors, thus a low-order representation might encode the bulk of the dynamically-relevant features. In this work, this operation is performed via snapshot POD implementation [35] based on the available non-time-resolved PIV velocity fields.

Assume U_{PIV} is a snapshot matrix of size $N_t \times N_c \times N_p$, with N_t being the number of snapshots, N_p the number of PIV grid points and N_c the number of measured components (2 for planar PIV, 3 for stereoscopic or volumetric PIV). The snapshot matrix is arranged with the generic j^{th} row being $U_{PIV,j} = \{(U(\mathcal{T}_j, \mathcal{X}_i), V(\mathcal{T}_j, \mathcal{X}_i))_{i=1}^{N_p}\}$, where U, V are the two velocity components for planar PIV, \mathcal{T}_j

Fig. 1. Sketch of the multi-time delay MLP combined with a PINN. The inputs of the system are local time-resolved consecutive velocity measurements by fast probes, outputting time-resolved velocity fields. The MLP functions as a POD encoder for the flow field information given time-resolved data from local fast probes and spatially-resolved PIV information. PINN acts as a regularizer for the flow field guaranteeing compliance with NS equations.

is the discrete time and λ_i is the discrete location of the measurement (consisting of two coordinates for planar PIV). The velocity components only refer to the fluctuations with respect to the average velocity field in each direction, i.e. the mean value of each velocity component is removed from all the data points measured via PIV. The POD of \mathcal{U}_{PIV} can be computed as the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), namely:

$$\mathcal{U}_{PIV} = \Psi_{PIV} \Sigma_{PIV} \Phi_{PIV}^T, \tag{1}$$

where Ψ_{PIV} and Φ_{PIV} are unitary square matrices of dimensions $N_t \times N_t$ and $N_c N_p \times N_c N_p$, respectively, and Σ_{PIV} is a diagonal matrix of dimensions $N_t \times N_c N_p$ whose elements are singular values. The matrices Ψ_{PIV} and Φ_{PIV} contain the temporal and spatial modes, respectively. However, as most often in PIV applications $N_t < N_c N_p$, we use the reduced version of SVD, in which matrices Ψ_{PIV} , Σ_{PIV} and Φ_{PIV}^T have dimensions $N_t \times N_t$, $N_t \times N_t$ and $N_t \times N_c N_p$, respectively. The columns of Ψ_{PIV} contain the temporal history of each POD mode, with the same temporal resolution of the original PIV fields composing \mathcal{U}_{PIV} .

Time-resolved information is collected through the installation of fast pointprobes in the fluid domain. Practical limitations of setup complexity limit the number of probes that can be installed in a system (see e.g. [28], where the authors use 5 probes for a time-resolved flow estimation in a high-Reynolds-number pipe flow). In convection-dominated flows, this limitation can be however surpassed via the embedding of temporal information through virtual probes, which can therefore be used to reconstruct each snapshot with increased precision. This assumption has been used by several authors [22,23,27]. For linear methods, this strategy is equivalent to a multi-time-delay LSE [36,37] and it is well-known in climate science as multichannel singular spectrum analysis [38]. Nonlinear extensions of this approach based on recurrent neural networks have also been explored [33,34]. In our implementation, for simplicity, probe data are fed as input to a multilayer perceptron (MLP), whose output after training will be the time coefficients of the most energetic POD temporal modes of the velocity field weighted with their corresponding singular

value, $A = \Psi \Sigma$. The number of modes R is selected by identifying the minimum amount which covers up to a certain level of cumulative energy (by default 90%) following the procedure explained in the Annex A at the end of this article. As a result, matrix A_{PIV} corresponding to the POD of the PIV snapshot matrix has dimensions $N_t \times R$. Bear in mind that this truncated version of the matrix is readily used for the training process of the MLP, i.e. the truncation of the full matrix A_{PIV} to rank R occurs prior to the training of the MLP, so that its output has automatically the truncated dimension R .

The model is trained on a set of probe and PIV data captured synchronously, i.e. in a common time reference. Probes are set to capture data at a higher frequency than snapshot PIV. This temporal information is fed to the MLP estimator with a multi-time delay embedding described in the following Section 2.2 and analogously to the virtual-probe procedure used by other authors for linear methods [22,23,27,28]. After training, the MLP is able to assimilate a set of sequences of probe recordings with the associated weighted temporal modes. Thus, given any other set of sequences of probe recordings at any other time and with the same sampling frequency, the MLP model is trained to predict the temporal modes \tilde{A}_{TR} of the associated velocity field. Note that this set of sequences to obtain time-resolved information does not necessarily include the ones used during training (although time-supersampling of the original sequence could be also performed). All the estimations presented in this work are carried out using probe recordings that are not exploited in training.

The rationale behind using POD as a field encoder resides in its simplicity of embedding high-dimensional information (2D PIV data can easily provide $\mathcal{O}(10^4)$ vectors per snapshot) in a lower-rank space, which simplifies the learning process and eases the convergence. Nonlinear techniques, e.g. autoencoders [39] or isometric feature mappings [40], are becoming increasingly popular in the fluid mechanics community and could be possible alternatives for future extensions of the architecture presented here. The reader is referred to the interesting literature review in [41] for an overview. On the other hand, the time information could be embedded with other solutions, such as LSTM neural networks [42–44], as already discussed in the introduction. Here, the use of MLP is motivated by its simplicity of implementation and its integration with the PINNs architecture, both of them based on fully-connected neural networks, although in future works recurrent architectures may be considered.

Once this approximate time-resolved matrix \tilde{A}_{TR} is obtained (bear in mind that the dimensions of \tilde{A}_{TR} correspond to $N_{test} \times R$, being N_{test} the number of time-resolved subsequent snapshots to be reconstructed), the full velocity field may be recovered on the same grid as the original PIV using Eq. (1), i.e. $\tilde{U}_{TR} = \tilde{A}_{TR} \Phi_{PIV}^T$. Note that, here, matrix Φ_{PIV}^T needs to be truncated to rank R so that dimensions match for a proper multiplication of matrices, i.e. Φ_{PIV}^T has new dimensions $R \times N_c N_p$. The average velocity value in each direction needs to be added back to recover the full velocity field. The approximated time-resolved velocity field \tilde{U}_{TR} is now resolved both in space and time, but lacks precision due to accumulation of errors from several sources, highlighting above all POD truncation and inaccuracies in the temporal-mode estimation with the MLP. To provide further precision and regularize the estimated fields to compensate for those errors, a PINN is used to improve the accuracy of the fluid domain with the regularization being based on the physical constraint of Eq. (2):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \ (e_1) \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \left(u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right) = 0 \ (e_2) \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \left(u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} - \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} \right) = 0 \ (e_3) \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \left(u \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial z^2} \right) = 0 \ (e_4), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where t, x, y, z , refer to dimensionless time and Cartesian coordinates; u, v, w indicate the normalized velocity components along x, y, z ; the normalized pressure is indicated with p , and $Re = U_\infty L / \nu$ is the Reynolds number based on a characteristic velocity U_∞ , length L and kinematic viscosity ν . Residuals are indicated between parenthesis as e_i ($i = 1, \dots, 4$) and their definition will be later explained in detail in Section 2.2. For applications to planar PIV (assuming for simplicity $x - y$ being the plane of the PIV measurement), the last equation and all terms involving derivatives along z must be neglected. In case stereoscopic measurements are not available, also all terms with w should be eliminated. This introduces a loss of accuracy and it is a limitation of the method to flow cases that are at least 2D on average if only planar PIV measurements are available.

If pressure boundary conditions are additionally accessible, PINNs may also augment the data by disclosing the pressure field p . It must be remarked that p could also be estimated directly from the time-resolved velocity field from the integration of the pressure gradient field (see for instance [26], in which fields estimated with EPOD are used to integrate the momentum equation and obtain pressure fields). Our hypothesis is that carrying out the process directly with the PINN includes further regularization, and thus has the potential to provide more accurate pressure fields.

2.2. Training procedure

The training of MLP and PINN is carried out separately. For the MLP, it is based on a simple cost function aiming at the minimization of the error in the reconstruction of A_{PIV} receiving as input a time segment of the probe data. The loss function \mathcal{L} is based on the mean squared error (MSE) between the real and predicted values divided by the corresponding Pearson correlation coefficient r , namely:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{N_t R r} \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^R (\tilde{a}_{i,j} - a_{i,j})^2, \quad (3)$$

where $a_{i,j}$ and $\tilde{a}_{i,j}$ are the real and predicted components of matrix A_{PIV} , respectively.

The choice of the segment depends on the location of the probes. In a convection-dominated flow, a typical choice is to locate the probes at the downstream end of the domain [26,27], although probes could also be installed at the wall [23,45]. In this work, we will consider the first configuration, and assign to each PIV snapshot a segment of the temporal sequence starting at the time of the PIV snapshot and extending for a throughflow time of the domain, similar to [27]. Therefore, if we pick snapshot time \mathcal{T}_k , then the probe data sequence is of the form $\{(U(\mathcal{T}_k, \mathcal{X}_{pr,i}), V(\mathcal{T}_k, \mathcal{X}_{pr,i}))_{i=1}^{N_{pr}}, \dots, (U(\mathcal{T}_k + q\tau, \mathcal{X}_{pr,i}), V(\mathcal{T}_k + q\tau, \mathcal{X}_{pr,i}))_{i=1}^{N_{pr}}\}$, where $\mathcal{X}_{pr,i}$ is the location of i^{th} probe, N_{pr} the number of probes, $\tau = \mathcal{T}_{k+1} - \mathcal{T}_k$ the time interval between two consecutive time-resolved probe measurements, and q the number of subsequent instances of data collection for the k^{th} PIV snapshot. The network is trained to estimate the temporal modes multiplied by their respective singular value, i.e. A . The rationale behind this choice is to give more importance to correctly estimate low-order modes, which contain the bulk of the energy.

Concerning the PINN, the loss function \mathcal{L} contains three main contributions:

- the residual of the NS equations following Eq. (2), \mathcal{L}_{NS} , computed both on the target refined grid and PIV grid to reduce truncation errors,
- the error with respect to the reference PIV velocity data given on the PIV grid, \mathcal{L}_{PIV} ,
- and, if available, a boundary condition on pressure at any given point or set of points, \mathcal{L}_p . This boundary condition could arise from direct measurement of the pressure in points of the domain (not necessarily the boundaries) and/or from reasonable assumptions on its boundaries.

The residual of the NS equations is computed by the MSE of each equation independently. This MSE is computed in the following form:

$$\text{MSE}(\tilde{Z}, Z) = \frac{1}{N_t N_p} \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} (\tilde{Z}(\mathcal{T}_i, \mathcal{X}_j) - Z(\mathcal{T}_i, \mathcal{X}_j))^2, \quad (4)$$

where Z and \tilde{Z} correspond to the real and predicted values of a particular magnitude. For the case of 2D configuration, the NS equations reduce to 3 equations, i.e. continuity and the two momentum equations, thus resulting in $\mathcal{L}_{NS} = \text{MSE}(e_1, 0) + \text{MSE}(e_2, 0) + \text{MSE}(e_3, 0)$, where 0 would be the reference residual value if NS were to be perfectly complied with (real value) and e_1, e_2 and e_3 the residuals of the NS equations from the predicted model, i.e. the error committed when predicted values of velocity and pressure are incorporated in the NS equations during training. Similarly, \mathcal{L}_{PIV} and \mathcal{L}_p are also calculated via MSE between the predicted quantities and the reference PIV and pressure values, correspondingly. Note that PIV and pressure data might be affected by uncertainty, i.e. in principle, even in the case of perfect assimilation and exact estimation of the velocity field, the loss function would not be zero. Furthermore, the truncation to a finite number of POD modes also generates a residual of the NS equations. This source of error might be mitigated by using a projection of the NS on the latent space during training. Since this process is dependent on the choice of the latent space for the mapping, in this work we use the full NS equations as physical constraints, and leave this possibility to future work.

In previous studies, the total loss is typically computed as the sum of the three contributions here indicated, see e.g. [5]. However, in this work we decided to opt for an adaptive-weighted error function, i.e. the weight of each error contribution is tuned during the training process. More specifically, the error with the higher value is adapted with the higher weight following a direct proportionality rule, i.e. $\mathcal{L} = w_{NS}\mathcal{L}_{NS} + w_{PIV}\mathcal{L}_{PIV} + w_p\mathcal{L}_p$, where $w_* = \mathcal{L}_*/(\mathcal{L}_{NS} + \mathcal{L}_{PIV} + \mathcal{L}_p)$. Therefore, the total loss may be written in a simplified manner as $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}_{NS}^2 + \mathcal{L}_{PIV}^2 + \mathcal{L}_p^2)/(\mathcal{L}_{NS} + \mathcal{L}_{PIV} + \mathcal{L}_p)$. The reason behind this approach in the description of the loss function is based on the compensation between two main counteractive effects during training: on the first hand, enforcing compliance with the NS equations tends to homogenize the outcome of the neural network, whereas on the other hand, the input of reference data imposes that the solution complies with experimentally-accessible data (which, as discussed above, are not necessarily accurate). In our experience, in the first part of the PINN training process, the effort is directed towards matching the estimation with the available experimental data (i.e. minimizing \mathcal{L}_{PIV}). As \mathcal{L}_{PIV} is reduced, \mathcal{L}_{NS} gains progressively relative importance and the physics constraints start regularizing the data.

Strictly speaking, the only necessary reference data would be the velocity field, since the reference pressure values are only required if the pressure field wants to be reconstructed. PINNs provide the pressure gradient, and therefore, information at any arbitrary point in the domain would suffice for a full reconstruction, although including constraints on all boundaries might help the convergence. Indeed, the continuity equation would already regularize the velocity field, whereas the addition of the momentum equations adds up to the strength of regularization while disclosing the pressure gradient. It must be remarked, however, that suitable boundary conditions for the pressure should be set at least in a point. The pressure gradient in the loss function indeed works as a ‘residual drain’, i.e. if unconstrained, it will incorporate errors due to inaccuracy of the other terms of the momentum equation, or due to missing terms (e.g. in the case of out-of-plane motion when using purely 2D measurements). Increasing the availability of points disclosing pressure reference values helps the convergence and improves the reconstruction of the flow, since the existence of pressure reference data constrains the accumulation of residuals in the pressure gradient, enhancing the regularization of the velocity fields as well.

3. Validation with the synthetic test case

3.1. Settings of the simulation and training

To validate our proposed architecture, we make use of synthetic data calculated via direct numerical simulation (DNS) of a fluid flow around a pinball configuration [46], i.e. three cylinders of diameter D located at the vertexes of an equilateral triangle with

lateral distance $l = 3/2D$ and origin of coordinates at the midpoint between the two rear cylinders. In that configuration, the centers of the cylinders are located at $[-3\sqrt{3}D/4, 0]$, $[0, 3D/4]$ and $[0, -3D/4]$. The simulation consists of 20,000 snapshots of a fluid flow at $Re = 130$ (i.e. in the so-called chaotic regime) with Cartesian coordinates $X \in [-5D, 15D]$ and $Y \in [-5D, 5D]$, and time interval between snapshots of $\tau = 0.1$ simulation units.

Time-resolved point velocity information is computed by extracting data at 5 positions at the downstream edge of the domain ($X = 15D$) and equally spaced in the vertical direction in the range $[1D, 5D]$. This replicates a realistic configuration in which the intrusiveness of the point probes should be minimized.

To obtain synthetic PIV data, we discretize the domain with 1024×512 pixels, thus corresponding to 51.2 pixels/ D . The domain is randomly seeded with particles with a density of 0.01 particles per pixel. Each virtual particle samples directly the velocity field. To resemble a velocity field similar to the typical PIV output, the PIV process is modeled as a moving average of the particles' velocity over bins (referred to as 'interrogation windows' in the PIV community). The average velocity value of each interrogation window is placed at its center. By default, this averaging bin or interrogation window is set to 32×32 pixels, with a 50% overlap. This overlap indicates that the grid distance of vectors is 16 pixels, i.e. one half of the linear size of the window, thus resulting in bins overlapped by 50% in each linear dimension. To account for potential experimental error, random normal (Gaussian) noise up to 20% of the value of the freestream velocity U_∞ may be added to the averaged value calculated via the interrogation window.

The point probes record velocity and pressure information at full time resolution, i.e. the data corresponding to the probe location is saved for 19,000 DNS snapshots, whereas the last 1,000 snapshots are left apart for testing purposes. This approach corresponds to a single-shot validation. This strategy was preferred to popular alternatives such as k-fold cross validation and recycle validation [47] to minimize the computational cost of the training. More robust validation strategies, however, could potentially provide better results for complex flows and noisy training data.

Random Gaussian noise of different intensities (as specified below) is added to explore the robustness to noise. Non-time-resolved PIV snapshots are generated by considering a time separation of 93 DNS time steps. This interval guarantees that the synthetic PIV does not have sufficient time resolution to discretize the dynamics of the flow. A total of 205 virtual PIV snapshots is thus generated. The synthetic PIV fields are analyzed with POD to extract the temporal modes weighted with the corresponding singular values A_{PIV} . In order to reduce the dimensionality of the problem, a rank truncation is performed based on the methodology explained in the Annex A, in which the number of modes for the best-case scenario with no noise can be found at $R = 11$ increasing up to $R = 158$ for a 20% noise. The main advantage of using POD as an encoder is the dimensionality reduction of the output, being it fixed at R coefficients corresponding to the most energetic modes.

The flow throughtime from the rear cylinders to the downstream edge of the domain corresponds to approximately $q = 150$ DNS snapshots. This throughtime originates from the fact that the convective velocity corresponds to $1D$ per simulation unit, the length of the field past the cylinders is $15D$ and the interval between snapshots is $\tau = 0.1$ simulation units. Therefore, on average a total of $q = 150$ snapshots is necessary to track the motion of a particle through the domain. Thus, the temporal mode estimator, i.e. the MLP, is fed by probe data from the $q = 150$ time instants past each considered PIV snapshot. This strategy corresponds to a time-delay approach in convection-dominated flows in which the selected timespan corresponds to one convective flow throughtime (as suggested in [27]) accounting for the portion of the domain past the rear cylinders.

The MLP architecture consists of a set of four fully-connected dense layers of decreasing number of neurons. More specifically, the number of neurons decreases from an initial amount of $2 \times N_{pr} \times q$ (where $N_{pr} = 5$ corresponds to the number of fast probes installed in the domain and $q = 150$) to a final dense layer with dimensions the number of weighted temporal modes to estimate, R . Each layer is activated differently: the first layer uses an hyperbolic tangent, the second a sigmoid and the last two a rectified linear unit function. The combined used of hyperbolic tangent and sigmoid intends to benefit for the fast learning capabilities of the hyperbolic tangent during the early stages of training, whereas sigmoid, due to its smoother derivative during backward propagation, allows for a steadier convergence when the minimum of the loss function is being approached. We opted for an Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} which is subsequently decreased parallel to the decrease of the training loss to allow for the optimal reconstruction based on empirical tests. This pyramidal structure encourages a fast and steady convergence given the significant reduction of the order of magnitude between the dimensionality of the input as compared to the output variables.

Once the temporal resolution of the probes has been embedded into the velocity fields with the MLP, we implement a PINN to enhance the accuracy by adding physical constraints. Our model for PINN consists of a fully-connected neural network with 10 hidden layers, each of them containing 100 nodes for each output variable, i.e. for a 2D domain, we have 300 nodes corresponding to the two components of velocity and pressure. The same optimizer as for the MLP is implemented here, whereas the activation function has been chosen to be a hyperbolic tangent with the exception of the last two layers, which are activated linearly. We use for training of the PINN the outcome of the MLP on the test dataset, which was never incorporated into the system during the MLP training phase. This is representative of the case of direct use of PINNs from probe data. Obviously, this same process could have been carried out by considering the training data, although in this case higher accuracy is expected for in-sample snapshots. In addition, to allow for a full reconstruction and extraction of the pressure field (note again that this is an additional feature, not available in the first place from PIV measurements), we use as boundary condition the pressure values given at the position of the probes, as if they were able to measure velocity and pressure simultaneously. For simplicity purposes, these pressure measurements have not been affected by noise to facilitate a proper reconstruction of the pressure field. Therefore, the deviation with respect to the DNS data may only be associated with errors occurring during the PINN training phase and the enforcement of the NS equations. We highlight that this boundary condition could have been exchanged by any other pressure measurement at any point within the domain.

Fig. 2. Flow field reconstruction via MLP+PINN. DNS and PIV truncated to rank $R = 31$ are included as reference. The fields are represented in their normalized version, i.e. $u = U/U_\infty$, $v = V/U_\infty$, $p = (P - P_\infty)/(\rho U_\infty^2)$ across the dimensionless coordinates $x = X/D$ and $y = Y/D$. Data represented for the case with a noise level of 5%. A video named *case31.mp4* of the fluid motion over one convective time is included as supplementary material.

3.2. Results

The flow field reconstruction quality for the test case of the fluidic pinball is assessed in this section. Fig. 2 shows contour plots of an instantaneous snapshot from the test dataset reconstructed using the proposed architecture with 5% (with respect to the nominal freestream velocity) added noise. Data are presented in non-dimensional form using the cylinder diameter D as reference length, and the freestream velocity U_∞ as reference velocity. For the pressure, data are normalized with respect to ρU_∞^2 , being the density ρ equal to 1 in the simulation. The plots show the streamwise and crosswise components of the velocity field with its corresponding pressure field. For the sake of comparison, we additionally present the associated DNS and PIV fields, even though this information was never included in the training dataset and works only as a qualitative estimate and reference. The synthetic PIV field has been projected on the POD basis computed from the training dataset and truncated to include the same number of modes R which will be estimated by the MLP. The figure shows the computed velocity fields via the MLP and the ones after applying the regularization with the PINN. The pressure field of the MLP is obtained from the integration of the pressure gradient computed with the momentum equation in (2) through a robust iterative procedure following the implementation by [26], which considers Neumann boundary conditions at all boundaries. For the case of the PINN, on the other hand, the only values for the pressure used during training are those recorded by the virtual probes at the exit of the domain, with no other boundary conditions being imposed. From a qualitative inspection, there is an excellent agreement between the data estimated via MLP, the data improved by the PINN and the target data. The improvement of the PINN is even more evident in the case of the pressure field, in which the process of estimation of the pressure is more robust than the one by direct integration of the momentum equations. PINNs may also allow the refinement of the original grid as compared to that of the original PIV, disclosing accurate flow information with finer detail.

A quantitative analysis of the reconstruction error using only the MLP estimator and combining it with the PINN is reported in Fig. 3. Fig. 3(a) shows the temporal root mean squared error ($RMSE_{\mathcal{T}}$) distribution computed on the $N_{\text{test}} = 150$ reconstructed snapshots in the testing database, namely:

$$RMSE_{\mathcal{T}}(\tilde{Z}(\mathcal{X}), Z(\mathcal{X})) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\text{test}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{test}}} (\tilde{Z}(\mathcal{T}_i, \mathcal{X}) - Z(\mathcal{T}_i, \mathcal{X}))^2}. \tag{5}$$

Note that in the above definition, the error is calculated for each position through all the times available. From a direct inspection of the figure, it can be noticed that after the MLP reconstruction, the main sources of error are associated with the finite spatial resolution of the PIV fields used for training, and therefore, the major errors are observed in presence of large velocity gradients, especially in the near field. In addition, truncation to rank R of the POD coefficients and temporal inconsistencies due to the finite accuracy of the estimation process add up to the reconstruction error. The error map looks similar for the case of the PINN estimator, although lower levels of error are observed in the freestream and in the far wake. A larger improvement is observed in the pressure field estimation by imposing physical constraints in the reconstruction process, together with a regularization of the velocity fields

Fig. 3. (a) Temporal root mean squared error (RMSE_T) over 150 test snapshots per grid point after MLP (upper row) and MLP+PINN (lower row) reconstruction of the flow field. (b) Spatial root mean square error (RMSE_x) for each reconstructed snapshot. Both errors in (a) and (b) have been normalized with the standard deviation of the velocity and pressure fluctuations of the original DNS.

by partially compensating noise. It must be remarked, however, that the PINN implementation allows imposing direct compliance with measured pressure in more than one point. A quantitative analysis is also reported in Fig. 3(b), where the spatial RMSE, namely,

$$RMSE_{\mathcal{X}}(\hat{Z}(\mathcal{T}), Z(\mathcal{T})) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_p} \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (\hat{Z}(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{X}_i) - Z(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{X}_i))^2}, \quad (6)$$

is depicted for each snapshot. A clear reduction of the error with respect to the estimation with the MLP is observed for both velocity components and for the pressure. Interestingly enough, PINNs are able to smooth out temporal variations and reduce the oscillations of the error, which would have inevitably compromised the computation of temporal derivatives. This is a clear advantage, considering that the estimation of derived quantities often relies on the estimation of time derivatives from temporally-resolved data.

The independent contributions to the total loss function during the training phase of the PINN are depicted in Fig. 4. The decrease in the total loss function indicates that the reconstructed fields from the MLP are being continuously regularized by enforcing compliance with the NS equations via the PINN. Nevertheless, the training loss reaches a plateau at approximately 500 epochs, which makes further iterations meaningless since they would not result in a significant improvement in accuracy. In our experience, this plateau is the result of a compromise between the tendency of the PINN to reduce residuals by homogenizing the estimated fields due to the enforcement of the NS equations, and the enforced compliance with the data estimated by the MLP.

It must be remarked that, in order to avoid convergence of the PINN to undesired local minima (the trivial one being a homogeneous field, with null gradient and, thus, perfect compliance with the NS equations), it is important to achieve a sufficiently good reconstruction with the MLP. We include the total root mean square error (considering both temporal and spatial dimensions, i.e. $RMSE = \sqrt{MSE}$ – refer to Eq. (4) for the definition of MSE –) for velocity components and pressure in cases with different spatial averaging and noise levels in Table 1. The table is classified according to different categories: the case starting with 1 refers to the perfect assimilation of DNS data onto the PIV grid; cases starting with 2 present velocity fields by using different sizes of

Fig. 4. Loss function and its individual contributions during the training stage of the PINN. As a reference, we include the error contributions to the loss function when the standard sum of components, i.e. $\mathcal{L} = \sum \mathcal{L}_i$, is used instead of the one proposed in this article (dashed curves). The compensating game between the enforcement of the NS constraints and the compliance with the reference velocity and pressure field is therefore essential for a proper reconstruction, especially in the cases in which higher noise is found within the reference data.

Table 1

Total RMSE (in both spatial and temporal dimensions) of different case scenarios normalized with the standard deviation of the corresponding field quantities from the DNS simulation. **Case 1:** direct projection of the DNS on the PIV grid, no added noise. **Case 21:** synthetic PIV with 32-px interrogation window, no added noise. **Case 22:** synthetic PIV with 64-px interrogation window, no added noise. **Case 31:** synthetic PIV with 32-px interrogation window and 5% added Gaussian noise. **Case 32:** synthetic PIV with 32-px interrogation window and 10% added Gaussian noise. **Case 33:** synthetic PIV with 32-px interrogation window and 20% added Gaussian noise. Each case has a complementary video (named accordingly to each case) showing the fluid motion over one convective time.

Case	NN	RMSE/std (u)	RMSE/std (v)	RMSE/std (p)
Case 1	MLP	0.1635	0.5260	0.5408
	PINN	0.1731	0.5589	0.3655
Case 21	MLP	0.1902	0.5129	0.5500
	PINN	0.1863	0.5360	0.3652
Case 22	MLP	0.2857	0.5177	0.6157
	PINN	0.2450	0.5192	0.3963
Case 31	MLP	0.1786	0.4939	0.5560
	PINN	0.1714	0.5107	0.3364
Case 32	MLP	0.2243	0.6568	0.7058
	PINN	0.1922	0.6320	0.4392
Case 33	MLP	0.3443	0.9782	1.2951
	PINN	0.2363	0.8040	0.6327

interrogation window, and therefore address resolution effects; cases starting with 3 focus on the effect of adding Gaussian noise to the synthetic PIV (fixed interrogation window of 32 pixels).

The results show that the regularization using PINNs is rather limited when the reference data from training of the MLP is accurate enough, e.g. case 1, in which the training data are directly sampled from the DNS on the PIV grid, and cases 21 and 31, in which none to only very mild levels of noise effects are included. In all the 3 cases the training data are of sufficient quality to properly train the MLP in the estimation, which is already remarkably accurate due to the low rank of the fields to be reconstructed. In these cases, however, a more significant improvement in the accuracy of pressure estimation is observed, most likely due to the enforcement of different boundary conditions. In the presence of probes, Dirichlet boundary conditions are imposed at the probe locations by the PINN, while in the direct integration we impose Neumann conditions on all boundaries. Furthermore, the smoothing effect of PINN on the velocity fields is beneficial in the estimation of the pressure.

In cases where the precision of PIV is lower, such as cases 22 (large averaging window), 32 and 33 (high noise level), the regularization with PINNs of the MLP data provides a significant improvement in accuracy, especially on the streamwise velocity component and the pressure. It can be hypothesized that most of the improvement arises from the suppression of random noise. This effect is particularly beneficial when computing derivatives. It is worth mentioning that noise reduction originates mostly from PINN implementation rather than MLP assimilation of temporal modes with truncation to rank R . Indeed, the estimated field after MLP conserves the bulk of uncertainty due to noise than that of the original PIV information used for training.

Fig. 5. Instantaneous streamwise/crosswise velocity components and pressure gradient fields. The first and second rows include, respectively, the original PIV snapshot and the POD-truncated reconstruction retaining 90% of the energy. The third row is the reconstruction by MLP. The last row shows the data of the MLP regularized with the PINN. A video named *airfoil2D.mp4* of the fluid motion over one convective time is included in the supplementary material.

4. Experimental application in the wake of a wing

The proposed architecture of flow estimator based on an MLP and regularized with a PINN is tested on the experimental test case of the wake past a NACA 0018 profile proposed in [26]. The experiments were carried out in the water tunnel of the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid and consisted of planar PIV measurements. The wing chord was $c = 0.08$ m and the freestream velocity was set to $U_\infty = 0.06$ m/s. The kinematic viscosity was measured to be the standard at 20 °C, i.e. $\nu = \rho/\mu = 10^{-6}$ m²/s. This results in a Reynolds number approximately equal to 3670.

The PIV field of view covers $x = X/c \in [0, 1.2]$ and $y = Y/c \in [-0.5, 0.5]$, with the origin being located at the trailing edge of the airfoil. While the original data were sampled at $1/\tau = 30$ Hz, the sequence fed to the MLP is downsampled by a factor of 3, which is sufficiently large to compromise the accuracy of time derivatives. In total, 2080 snapshots were available for training, while 190 snapshots at full-time resolution were kept for test purposes. Probe data has been artificially computed by sampling flow velocity from the original dataset at 30 Hz in 5 locations regularly spaced along the vertical direction at the downstream side of the field of view and ranging from $Y = -5c$ to $Y = 5c$. The MLP is fed by temporal sequences of $q = 61$ samples at $1/\tau = 30$ Hz. This corresponds to one convective time throughout the domain. While the MLP estimates data on the same grid as the original PIV, the PINN is trained on a finer grid (with points with equal spacing in both directions and grid refinement 3.5 times smaller than the original PIV one) to allow more accurate derivative calculation. The same architecture and training procedure of the test case of the fluidic pinball wake has been used.

Fig. 5 shows the original PIV data of the corresponding snapshot and its truncated POD reconstruction accounting for 90% of energy. The reconstruction of the MLP and PINN only receives as input probe data from the test dataset once the MLP has been trained on the available PIV training data, therefore we are avoiding any occurrence of overfitting. The reconstruction of the absolute pressure field has not been carried out here due to the absence of a reliable pressure boundary condition. Fig. 5 however shows the evolution of the two in-plane components of the pressure gradient, p_x and p_y . The PINN provides a direct estimate of the pressure gradients by enforcing NS equations during training, whereas for PIV and MLP the pressure gradient has been computed as residuals from the NS equations.

It must be remarked that PINNs are not able to fully recover flow structures that may have been lost during the process of PIV data acquisition or estimation from the MLP. Therefore, the improvement due to the regularization of the PINN is sensitive to the quality of the estimated data. The reference experimental PIV data is affected by two main sources of error: noise (and in general all uncertainty sources of PIV measurements) and assumption of 2D velocity field (i.e. the terms of the NS equations including the out-of-plane velocity component are neglected). We have compared the outcome of directly imposing PINNs over the original reference PIV data and over the original reference data truncated at 90% of the energy, and the results prove significantly closer to ground truth in those cases (see Fig. 6). While in this case the PINN could have been applied also on non-time-resolved data to impose zero divergence, it must be remarked that in case a pressure boundary condition is available at one or more points, a further benefit can be obtained by imposing also the momentum equations. This could be performed thanks to the temporal resolution enabled by the MLP fed by the probe data.

Fig. 6. PINN application over the original PIV sequence, PIV truncated to 90% of the energy, and the time-resolved sequence estimated by the MLP. First line of plots shows the recorded PIV experiment for reference purposes, where p_x and p_y are computed by application of NS equations. A video named *comparison.mp4* of the fluid motion over one convective time for each case is included together with this article.

Table 2
Total MSE between the reference velocity field (provided this time via MLP) and the reconstructed flow after PINN for each λ . Additionally, MSE of the residuals of the NS equations is included.

Case	MSE reference velocity	MSE NS
$\lambda = 1$	0.0116	0.0048
$\lambda = 0.1$	0.0114	0.0485
$\lambda = 0.01$	0.0115	0.4801

It is also worth noticing that the weight of the NS equations during the training process of the PINN plays a major role in the final output. We remind the reader that the loss function is defined by default as the sum of the three different sources of error in the system (residuals of the NS equations, error with respect to PIV data, error with respect to pressure probe information) weighted proportionally to their contribution to the total error. Fig. 7 shows the different outcomes when the NS residual is weighted by a factor $\lambda = 1, 0.1, 0.01$, being the new contribution to the total error computed as $\mathcal{L}'_{NS} = \lambda \mathcal{L}_{NS}$. This new definition implies that, for small λ , higher relevance is given to the compliance of the reconstructed field with the measured data rather than the enforcement of the NS equations. This might be needed in cases where the regularization imposed by compliance with the NS equations tends to oversmooth the data. The fluid reconstruction using the original loss function (corresponding to $\lambda = 1$) results in flow fields with weak gradients. While this provides low residuals of the NS equations, it might lead to a significant attenuation of the velocity fluctuation. The total MSE (both in temporal and spatial dimensions) with respect to the reference velocity field provided by MLP and the NS residual (or equivalently \mathcal{L}_{PIV} and \mathcal{L}_{NS} for the last epoch during PINN training) for each λ are indicated in Table 2. A low weight ($\lambda \leq 0.01$) is not recommended since the application of the NS constraints would not be effective and pressure reconstruction would be completely impeded, as we can see from Fig. 7 and values from Table 2.

5. Conclusions

We have proposed a solution to enable the estimation of flow fields from a small number of sensors in convection-dominated flows and increase the accuracy by embedding physical constraints with a physics-informed neural network. The proposed architecture leverages the capability of an MLP to precisely estimate temporal modes of POD and entrusts the output regularization to the PINN. POD allows for the identification of a compact low-dimensional embedding of the most relevant features of the flow fields, thus simplifying the task of building a mapping between probe data and fields. The input information is also enhanced using a multi-time delay approach under the hypothesis of convection-dominated flow.

The proposed concept allows the use of PINNs for regularization of snapshot PIV data, i.e. in the absence of temporal resolution, incorporating in the process also equations including temporal derivatives (such as the momentum equations). This enables the extraction of pressure fields by including proper boundary conditions in the training process. The obtained results show a significant accuracy enhancement of the predicted velocity fields from MLP after the PINN regularization, and a reasonably good accuracy for

Fig. 7. Reconstruction after MLP+PINN with different weight λ applied to the residual of the NS equations during the PINN training process. A video named *NSweight.mp4* of the fluid motion over one convective time for each case is included together with this article.

pressure field estimations. It must be remarked that the achievable improvement from the use of the PINN strongly depends on the quality of the estimated data with the MLP. This process has a higher probability of success in cases of flows evolving on low-dimensional attractors, or in general with clearly recognizable features, such as vortex shedding.

An oversmoothing effect of imposing compliance with the Navier–Stokes equations has also been observed, especially in cases in which the accuracy of the estimated fields with MLP was not sufficiently good. Tuning the loss term due to the residual of the NS equations in the experimental case of the wing profile has been shown to be only marginally beneficial. This is due to its reduced potential to regularize as a result of the absence of sufficiently accurate boundary conditions for the pressure term. The availability of pressure reference values is therefore of uttermost importance if an effective regularization through the momentum equation is sought. The tuning of this effect is out of the scope of this work and might be the object of future research.

We underline that the building blocks of the proposed method can be significantly improved while leveraging the same principle of using fast probes to disclose the time-resolution and an encoding/decoding procedure for the identification of a latent space to simplify the mapping from probe data. Nonlinear techniques for latent space identification based on convolutional autoencoders or manifold learning are becoming increasingly popular in turbulent flows [41,48–50]. More compact latent spaces are appealing to simplify the state estimation from probe data. Furthermore, the delay-embedding approach of this work is rather simple and mimics similar procedures used in virtual-probe generation of EPOD-based methods. Methods that are more suitable for the treatment of time-series, such as recurrent neural networks (see e.g. long short-term memory or echo state networks) or transformers, are expected to have superior performances. Furthermore, physical constraints might be straightforwardly embedded in the training of such architectures, as in physics-informed recurrent neural networks [51], especially if the governing equations can be directly formulated in the latent space. Future efforts might be oriented to the implementation in the proposed framework of deep autoencoder architectures and nonlinear time-series forecasting techniques to feed the PINN.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All datasets used in this work are openly available in Zenodo, accessible at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10214004>. All codes developed in this work are openly available in GitHub, accessible through the link <https://github.com/AlvaroMS90/Complete-flow-characterization-from-snapshot-PIV-fast-probes-and-physics-informed-neural-networks>.

Fig. 8. Cumulative energy per number of selected modes (top subplot) and representation of normalized squared singular values (bottom subplot). The dashed horizontal black line in the top subplot represents the threshold when 90% of the cumulative energy has been surpassed and the corresponding number of singular values R for each case is indicated via vertical dotted lines with matching colors. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3
Number of selected singular values R to reconstruct the velocity domains via the MLP recovering up to 90% of the cumulative energy.

Case	1	21	22	31	32	33	Airfoil
R	11	12	18	31	117	158	55

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Annex A

The number of modes R to truncate the dimensions of the matrices from the POD of the PIV dataset may be obtained by examination of the values of the singular values contained in matrix Σ_{PIV} . The cumulative energy from the flow information may be then calculated by

$$\sum_{i=1}^{R \leq N_t} \sigma_i^2 / \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \sigma_i^2, \tag{7}$$

where N_t is the total number of snapshots available from PIV (matrix Σ_{PIV} obtained by SVD has dimensions $N_t \times N_t$ when the number of datapoints per snapshots $N_c N_p$ is larger than N_t), and σ are the singular values contained in Σ_{PIV} . For our particular scenarios discussed in this article, N_t is 205 for the validation case, i.e. wake past a pinball configuration, and 2080 for the wing experiment. The cumulative energy distribution for different values of mode number is represented in Fig. 8. Table 3 summarizes the number of selected singular values R to reconstruct up to 90% of the cumulative energy via the MLP for each of the cases discussed in this article.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2023.116652>.

References

[1] S.L. Brunton, B.R. Noack, P. Koumoutsakos, Machine learning for fluid mechanics, *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* 52 (2020) 477–508, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev-fluid-010719-060214>.
 [2] S. Discetti, Y. Liu, Machine learning for flow field measurements: a perspective, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 34 (021001) (2023) 1–16, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/ac9991>.

- [3] R. Vinuesa, S.L. Brunton, Enhancing computational fluid dynamics with machine learning, *Nat. Comput. Sci.* 2 (2022) 358–366, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s43588-022-00264-7>.
- [4] M. Raissi, P. Perdikaris, G.E. Karniadakis, Physics-informed neural networks: a deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations, *J. Comput. Phys.* 378 (2019) 686–707, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2018.10.045>.
- [5] M. Raissi, A. Yazdani, G.E. Karniadakis, Hidden fluid mechanics: learning velocity and pressure fields from flow visualizations, *Science* 367 (6481) (2020) 1026–1030, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw4741>.
- [6] I.E. Lagaris, A. Likas, D.I. Fotiadis, Artificial neural networks for solving ordinary and partial differential equations, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.* 9 (5) (1998) 987–1000, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/72.712178>.
- [7] S. Cai, Z. Wang, S. Wang, P. Perdikaris, G.E. Karniadakis, Physics-informed neural networks for heat transfer problems, *J. Heat Transfer* 143 (6) (2021) 1–15, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1115/1.4050542>, (060801).
- [8] F. Sahli Costabal, Y. Yang, P. Perdikaris, D.E. Hurtado, E. Kuhl, Physics-informed neural networks for cardiac activation mapping, *Front. Phys.* 8 (42) (2020) 1–12, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2020.00042>.
- [9] G.S. Misyris, A. Venzke, S. Chatzivasileiadis, Physics-informed neural networks for power systems, in: 2020 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM), 2020, pp. 1–5, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/PESGM41954.2020.9282004>.
- [10] Y. Chen, L. Lu, G.E. Karniadakis, L.D. Negro, Physics-informed neural networks for inverse problems in nano-optics and metamaterials, *Opt. Express* 28 (8) (2020) 11618–11633, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/OE.384875>.
- [11] X.I.A. Yang, S. Zafar, J.-X. Wang, H. Xiao, Predictive large-eddy-simulation wall modeling via physics-informed neural networks, *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 4 (034602) (2019) 1–22, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.4.034602>.
- [12] Z. Mao, A.D. Jagtap, G.E. Karniadakis, Physics-informed neural networks for high-speed flows, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Engrg.* 360 (112789) (2020) 1–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2019.112789>.
- [13] S. Cai, Z. Mao, Z. Wang, M. Yin, G.E. Karniadakis, Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) for fluid mechanics: a review, *Acta Mech. Sin.* 37 (12) (2021) 1727–1738, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10409-021-01148-1>.
- [14] L. Lu, R. Pestourie, W. Yao, Z. Wang, F. Verdugo, S.G. Johnson, Physics-informed neural networks with hard constraints for inverse design, *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.* 43 (6) (2021) B1105–B1132, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1137/21M1397908>.
- [15] E. Zhang, M. Dao, G.E. Karniadakis, S. Suresh, Analyses of internal structures and defects in materials using physics-informed neural networks, *Sci. Adv.* 8 (7) (2022) 1–12, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abk0644>.
- [16] H. Eivazi, M. Tahani, P. Schlatter, R. Vinuesa, Physics-informed neural networks for solving Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations, *Phys. Fluids* 34 (075117) (2022) 1–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0095270>.
- [17] J. Han, D. Kim, H. Shin, K.C. Kim, Enhanced data assimilation of 4D LPT with physics informed neural networks, in: 14th International Symposium on Particle Image Velocimetry - ISPIV 2021, 2021.
- [18] H. Wang, Y. Liu, S. Wang, Dense velocity reconstruction from particle image velocimetry/particle tracking velocimetry using a physics-informed neural network, *Phys. Fluids* 34 (017116) (2022) 1–15, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0078143>.
- [19] G. Hasanuzzaman, H. Eivazi, S. Merbold, C. Egbers, R. Vinuesa, Enhancement of PIV measurements via physics-informed neural networks, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 34 (044002) (2023) 1–16, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/aca9eb>.
- [20] R.J. Adrian, Stochastic estimation of conditional structure: a review, *Appl. Sci. Res.* 53 (1994) 291–303, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00849106>.
- [21] J. Borée, Extended proper orthogonal decomposition: a tool to analyse correlated events in turbulent flows, *Exp. Fluids* 35 (2003) 188–192, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00348-003-0656-3>.
- [22] C.E. Tinney, L.S. Ukeiley, M.N. Glauser, Low-dimensional characteristics of a transonic jet. Part 2. Estimate and far-field prediction, *J. Fluid Mech.* 625 (2008) 53–92, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0022112008003601>.
- [23] Z. Hosseini, R.J. Martinuzzi, B.R. Noack, Sensor-based estimation of the velocity in the wake of a low-aspect-ratio pyramid, *Exp. Fluids* 56 (13) (2015) 1–16, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00348-014-1880-8>.
- [24] J.A. Bourgeois, B.R. Noack, R.J. Martinuzzi, Generalized phase average with applications to sensor-based flow estimation of the wall-mounted square cylinder wake, *J. Fluid Mech.* 736 (2013) 316–350, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2013.494>.
- [25] J.H. Tu, J. Griffin, A. Hart, C.W. Rowley, L.N. Cattafesta III, L.S. Ukeiley, Integration of non-time-resolved PIV and time-resolved velocity point sensors for dynamics estimation of velocity fields, *Exp. Fluids* 54 (1429) (2013) 1–20, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00348-012-1429-7>.
- [26] J. Chen, M. Raiola, S. Discetti, Pressure from data-driven-estimated velocity fields using snapshot PIV and fast probes, *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* 136 (110647) (2022) 1–13, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.exthermfluidsci.2022.110647>.
- [27] S. Discetti, M. Raiola, A. Ianiro, Estimation of time-resolved turbulent fields through correlation of non-time-resolved field measurements and time-resolved point measurements, *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* 93 (2018) 119–130, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.exthermfluidsci.2017.12.011>.
- [28] S. Discetti, G. Bellani, R. Örlü, J. Serpieri, C. Sanmiguel Vila, M. Raiola, X. Zheng, L. Mascotelli, A. Talamelli, A. Ianiro, Characterization of very-large-scale motions in high-Re pipe flows, *Exp. Therm. Fluid Sci.* 104 (2019) 1–8, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.exthermfluidsci.2019.02.001>.
- [29] N.B. Erichson, L. Mathelin, Z. Yao, S.L. Brunton, M.W. Mahoney, J.N. Kutz, Shallow neural networks for fluid flow reconstruction with limited sensors, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 476 (20200097) (2020) 1–25, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2020.0097>.
- [30] A. Güemes, S. Discetti, A. Ianiro, Sensing the turbulent large-scale motions with their wall signature, *Phys. Fluids* 31 (125112) (2019) 1–11, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.5128053>.
- [31] L. Guastoni, A. Güemes, A. Ianiro, S. Discetti, P. Schlatter, H. Azizpour, R. Vinuesa, Convolutional-network models to predict wall-bounded turbulence from wall quantities, *J. Fluid Mech.* 928 (A27) (2021) 1–37, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2021.812>.
- [32] A. Güemes, S. Discetti, A. Ianiro, B. Sirmacek, H. Azizpour, R. Vinuesa, From coarse wall measurements to turbulent velocity fields through deep learning, *Phys. Fluids* 33 (075121) (2021) 1–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0058346>.
- [33] Z. Deng, Y. Chen, Y. Liu, K.C. Kim, Time-resolved turbulent velocity field reconstruction using a long short-term memory (LSTM)-based artificial intelligence framework, *Phys. Fluids* 31 (075108) (2019) 1–12, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.5111558>.
- [34] X. Jin, S. Laima, W.-L. Chen, H. Li, Time-resolved reconstruction of flow field around a circular cylinder by recurrent neural networks based on non-time-resolved particle image velocimetry measurements, *Exp. Fluids* 61 (114) (2020) 1–23, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00348-020-2928-6>.
- [35] L. Sirovich, Turbulence and the dynamics of coherent structures. I. Coherent structures, *Quart. Appl. Math.* 45 (3) (1987) 561–571, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1090/qam/910462>.
- [36] D. Ewing, J.H. Citriniti, Examination of a LSE/POD complementary technique using single and multi-time information in the axisymmetric shear layer, in: J.N. Sørensen, E.J. Hopfinger, N. Aubry (Eds.), IUTAM Symposium on Simulation and Identification of Organized Structures in Flows, Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 1999, pp. 375–384, http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-4601-2_33.
- [37] C.E. Tinney, F. Coiffet, J. Delville, A.M. Hall, P. Jordan, M.N. Glauser, On spectral linear stochastic estimation, *Exp. Fluids* 41 (2006) 763–775, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00348-006-0199-5>.
- [38] M. Ghil, M.R. Allen, M.D. Dettinger, K. Ide, D. Kondrashov, M.E. Mann, A.W. Robertson, A. Saunders, Y. Tian, F. Varadi, P. Yiou, Advanced spectral methods for climatic time series, *Rev. Geophys.* 40 (1) (2002) 3–1–3–41, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2000RG000092>.
- [39] G. Alain, Y. Bengio, What regularized auto-encoders learn from the data-generating distribution, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 15 (1) (2014) 3563–3593, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5555/2627435.2750359>.

- [40] J.B. Tenenbaum, V. de Silva, J.C. Langford, A global geometric framework for nonlinear dimensionality reduction, *Science* 290 (2000) 2319–2323, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.290.5500.2319>.
- [41] M.A. Mendez, Linear and nonlinear dimensionality reduction from fluid mechanics to machine learning, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 34 (042001) (2023) 1–20, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/acaffe>.
- [42] S. Hochreiter, J. Schmidhuber, Long short-term memory, *Neural Comput.* 9 (8) (1997) 1735–1780, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>.
- [43] N. Kalchbrenner, I. Danihelka, A. Graves, Grid long-short term memory, 2015, arXiv: [arXiv:1507.01526v3](https://arxiv.org/abs/1507.01526v3).
- [44] K. Greff, R.K. Srivastava, J. Koutník, B.R. Steunebrink, J. Schmidhuber, LSTM: a search space odyssey, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.* 28 (10) (2017) 2222–2232, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2016.2582924>.
- [45] C. Sicot, R. Perrin, T.T. Tran, J. Borée, Wall pressure and conditional flow structures downstream of a reattaching flow region, *Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow* 35 (2012) 119–129, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2012.04.005>.
- [46] N. Deng, B.R. Noack, M. Morzyński, L.R. Pastur, Low-order model for successive bifurcations of the fluidic pinball, *J. Fluid Mech.* 884 (A37) (2020) 1–41, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2019.959>.
- [47] A. Racca, L. Magri, Robust optimization and validation of echo state networks learning chaotic dynamics, *Neural Netw.* 142 (2021) 252–268, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2021.05.004>.
- [48] H. Eivazi, S. Le Clainche, S. Hoyas, R. Vinuesa, Towards extraction of orthogonal and parsimonious non-linear modes from turbulent flows, *Expert Syst. Appl.* 202 (117038) (2022) 1–11, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.117038>.
- [49] H. Csala, S.T.M. Dawson, A. Arzani, Comparing different nonlinear dimensionality reduction techniques for data-driven unsteady fluid flow modeling, *Phys. Fluids* 34 (117119) (2022) 1–22, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0127284>.
- [50] E. Farzamnik, A. Ianiro, S. Discetti, N. Deng, K. Oberleithner, B.R. Noack, V. Guerrero, From snapshots to manifolds - a tale of shear flows, *J. Fluid Mech.* 955 (A34) (2023) 1–24, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2022.1039>.
- [51] Y. Zheng, C. Hu, X. Wang, Z. Wu, Physics-informed recurrent neural network modeling for predictive control of nonlinear processes, *J. Process Control* 128 (103005) (2023) 1–17, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jprocont.2023.103005>.